

Analysis of the Effect of Self Efficacy and Distributive Justice on Organizational Commitments in Improving Employees Performance at the Department of Youth Education and Sports in Bali Province

Ni Nengah Rai Yennie¹, Putu Kepra Maren², I Nengah Sudja³

^{1,2,3}Mahasaraswati University Denpasar

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of self-efficacy, distributive justice on organizational commitment and employee performance. The population in this study were employees of the Bali Provincial Education Office. The sampling technique used purposive sampling and obtained a sample of 74 respondents. The variables of this study used three variables, namely the dependent variable, the independent variable, and the mediating variable. The dependent variable (Y) of this study is employee performance. Independent variable (X) self efficacy and distributive justice. The mediating variable is organizational commitment (Z). The research method used is a quantitative method. For the data analysis method using Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis using Smart PLS Software. The results of this study indicate that, Self efficacy affects organizational commitment Distributive justice affects organizational commitment Self efficacy affects employee performance Distributive justice affects employee performance based on organizational commitment affects employee performance. Self efficacy has no effect on employee performance through organizational commitment as a mediating variable based on distributive justice affects employee performance through organizational commitment as a mediating variable

KEYWORDS: Self Efficacy, Distributive Justice, Organizational Commitment, and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are a central figure in organizations and companies. The higher the employee's ability, the higher the organizational performance. Vice versa, the lower the employee's ability, the lower the organizational performance. Kasager (2013) states that performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks that have been assigned to him based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time.

Organizational commitment can be used to predict professional activities and work behavior because organizational commitment reflects an individual's positive attitude towards the organization. In this way, knowledge and understanding of organizational commitment can be used as a basis for predicting individual work behavior (Sehertian and Soetjipto, 2011).

In addition to the important organizational commitment factor in influencing employee performance, it is also necessary to pay attention to the self-efficacy of the employees. Self-efficacy is a matter of belief in the individual's perceived ability to cope with special situations in connection with an assessment of the ability to perform an action related to a particular task or situation. (DeReMa Journal of Management Vol.12 No. 1, May 2017).

Self Efficacy is an individual's assessment of self-confidence in his ability to carry out tasks so as to obtain results as expected (Bandura, 1994). Someone who has high efficacy tends to use all the abilities they have to achieve the expected goals. In addition to self-efficacy, another factor that affects performance is distributive justice. According to Palupi et.al (2014) defines that distributive justice is justice related to the distribution of resources and the criteria used to determine the allocation of these resources. This type of justice concerns a person's perception of the fairness of the career they receive.

Injustice in the organization is one form of dysfunctional organizational practices that have an impact on an uncomfortable working atmosphere in the organization. Injustice and fairness are things that employees are very concerned about in relation to transactional processes in the organization. One of the organizational or company policies that become an important concern for employees is policies related to careers within the company (Tjahjono, 2007).

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Distributive justice can have a significant impact on long-term employee performance. Strong self-efficacy helps employee performance because it creates a level of motivation in employees. Shared perspectives make people feel comfortable working for an organization. A sense of commitment or loyalty makes people try harder.

This is as expressed by Budiarto (2005) that conceptually distributive justice is also related to the distribution of conditions and goods which will affect the welfare of the individual including physical, psychological, economic, and social aspects. The distributive goal here is welfare. Distributive justice refers to justice from the bottom level, which includes issues of remuneration, training, promotions, and dismissals. These policies must undergo changes due to mission factors and updated procedures.

The problem of organizational justice at the Department of Education, Youth and Sports of Bali Province is very influential on employee performance, this is in accordance with the results of research proposed by Hidayah and Haryani (2013); Nasuridin and Khuan (2007) which states that organizational justice has a positive effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, Suliman and Kathairi (2013), suggest that organizational justice through organizational commitment as an intervening variable has an influence on employee performance.

According to Nugraheni and Wijayanti (2009) stated that the distributive justice variable has more influence on performance than the procedural justice variable, it is evidenced by the correlation number between the distributive justice variable and performance is greater than the correlation between procedural justice and performance, it can be stated that the justice variable distributive has more influence on performance than the presedural justice variable.

Research by Warokka et al., (2012) shows the results that interactional justice is more influential than other types of organizational justice in evaluating employee performance. Employees are more concerned with interactions during and after the evaluation process. They are interested in knowing how they have been evaluated and what feedback there will be after the performance appraisal process.

The Department of Education, Youth and Sports of the Province of Bali is the agency responsible for carrying out development tasks in the field of education which refers to improving human resources with the main task of carrying out regional authority in the field of education. The education sector is a very important pillar in building the foundation for the Indonesian people to build Indonesian society towards a society that is resilient and able to compete in the free market era (Sutapa and Purwanto, 2012). So that in carrying out the task of giving the mandate and responsibility to the local government, so that the progress or not of an education in an area is also very dependent on the policies implemented in the area.

The function of the Department of Youth and Sports Education is to formulate technical policies in the field of education and to implement operational technical policies in the field of education. In its implementation, the Youth and Sports Education Office is led by the Head of the Service. The Head of the Bali Province Youth and Sports Education Office leads the employees with full responsibility. The Head of Service asks for active participation from employees in assisting decision-making, is democratic, becomes an example for employees, is fair to employees and has a vision for the future.

From the results of previous research on the effect of self-efficacy on organizational commitment according to Gillham, Reivich and Shatte (2002:121) stated that individuals with high self-efficacy have a commitment to solving problems and will not give up when they find that the strategy being used does not work. . In the context of the dynamics of organizational life, such commitment is needed, especially to solve various organizational problems, including the achievement of organizational goals.

Argawal and Misrha (2016) state that there is a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and organizational commitment, Self-efficacy is a person's belief about his ability to do a job. This belief encourages a person to work harder and turn an obstacle into a challenge for him. Self-efficacy also makes it easier for a person to adapt to the environment and more easily adapt to the values that exist in the organization which then makes members have better performance and evaluate an organization well so that those who have self-efficacy will tend to stay afloat. in an organization by developing the organization.

Employees who feel and believe that their abilities are able to form a sense of connectedness to the organization will consistently form organizational commitment in other words self-efficacy, namely employee confidence in the ability to complete their tasks, whether they have been directly committed to the organization, so it can be concluded that self-efficacy directly affects positively on organizational commitment and shows that self-efficacy has a positive effect on organizational commitment (Hassan, Kibriya and Nawaz, 2013: 948).

Wright and Noe (1996:353) explain self-efficacy which is a person's assessment of himself, whether he can successfully carry out an activity. Someone who has high self-efficacy will put more effort by overcoming the obstacles or obstacles he faces. Meanwhile, Baron (1996:393) views that self-efficacy is the ability that a person has to be able to carry out the desired action. The higher a person's feeling about his self-efficacy, the better his tendency to perform a wider variety of tasks.

Self efficacy is a person's ability which includes belief in being able to do something well, self-efficacy refers to an

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individual's belief about his ability to mobilize, motivation, cognitive resources, and actions needed to succeed in performing tasks in a particular context (Bandura, 1997). According to Sari (2014) individuals who have strong motivation, clear goals, stable emotions and also the ability will become better performance or individuals who have high self-efficacy.

Robbins and Judge (2011:251) self-efficacy is "an individual's belief that he or she is capable of performing a task". The point is that self-efficacy is the belief of an employee or individual that he is able to do a task well. Furthermore, according to Robbins and Judge (2013: 251-252), "the higher your self-efficacy, the higher the self-confidence, the higher the confidence you have in your ability to succeed in a task".

Explanation above shows that the success of an employee in the organization is also determined by his belief or belief that his abilities are a positive force in completing work. This means that, with the self-efficacy of employees, they will be able to form positive energy or intrinsic motivation (push within oneself) to carry out tasks in accordance with organizational goals.

Self-efficacy is the individual's capacity to stimulate his potential to continue to carry out the tasks/jobs assigned by the organization. Therefore, individuals who believe that they are able to carry out work in accordance with organizational goals, this means that an employee (individual) wants to involve himself or remains involved in the organization.

This also means that employees feel and believe that involvement in carrying out tasks in accordance with organizational goals is a form of self-efficacy to form organizational commitment. Related to the above, according to Robbins and Judge (2011:111) that organizational commitment is a condition where an employee favors a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in that organization.

Thus it is clear that organizational commitment can be formed by employees' feelings and beliefs about their ability to carry out their duties well. According to Luthans (2008:147): employee commitment is related to an employee's attitude related to a strong desire, willingness, and belief to remain a member of the organization, try their best, and still believe in the organization.

Employees who still feel and believe that their abilities are able to form a sense of attachment to the organization will consistently form organizational commitment. In other words, self-efficacy, namely the employee's belief in the ability to complete his duties, means that he has directly committed to the organization. Thus it can be concluded, self-efficacy directly affects positively and significantly organizational commitment as the results of research from Hassan, Kibriya and Nawaz (2013 :947-948) and Murthy (2014: 119-120) show that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

In addition, there is also a research gap on the effect of self-efficacy on employee performance. The results of research conducted by Hanum (2013) showed a positive and significant influence between self-efficacy and employee performance, the results of another study conducted by Sari (2014) showed a positive and significant influence between self-efficacy and employee performance, while the results of research conducted by Prasetya, et al (2013) show that self-efficacy has no effect on employee performance.

Another factor that can affect employee performance is distributive justice. Colquitt (2017) argues that distributive justice is the suitability of the results obtained based on what has been given by looking at those obtained by others, Steven L (2014) mentions that distributive justice refers to the organization by comparing the results that other people get. Based on the contribution they gave to the organization, Folgar (1989) explained that distributive justice refers to the perceived fairness based on the amount of compensation received by employees.

Ravangard et al., (2013) stated that organizational justice is a motivational tool and a factor that influences organizational commitment. Jawad et al., (2012) in their research that there is a significant influence between distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice on organizational commitment. Akuzum (2014) conducted a study with the results that there was a positive and significant effect between organizational justice and organizational commitment. Thus the 3rd (three) research above shows that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The commitment of employees to the company is certainly an important factor for a company. This will make it difficult for employees to leave the company and employees will feel obliged to achieve the goals of the company where they work. Luthans (2005:249) defines organizational commitment as follows: "A strong desire to remain as a member, a desire to strive according to the wishes of the organization, certain beliefs and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization." The forms of organizational commitment are active commitment, continuance commitment, normative commitment, continuous commitment, integrated commitment and controlled commitment. Kanter and Fairy in Sophia (2008: 158).

Kusnadi (2003: 264) explains that performance is a movement, action, implementation, activity or conscious action that is directed to achieve a certain goal or target. Performance is the result of work within a certain period both in quality and quantity achieved by a person or group of people in carrying out work tasks in accordance with the responsibilities that have been given

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to him. Mangkuprawira (2007: 155-156) explains that there are 5 factors that affect performance, namely personal factors (individual), leadership factors, team factors, system factors and contextual factors.

Commitment is an attitude shown by employees as a sense of loyalty to the company where they work. Loyalty can be seen from how much employees involve themselves in their work activities to achieve the goals of the company. High employee involvement shows that the employee will exert his ability to achieve the best results for the company, then this will affect employee performance. Yousef in Azzuhri (2012: 27). There is a positive and significant effect of organizational commitment on employee performance, namely good organizational commitment will significantly improve employee performance, and vice versa, poor organizational commitment will significantly reduce employee performance.

In previous studies often used the object of research in companies engaged in profit companies, namely companies whose main goal is to earn profits. As described by Putrana, et al (2016) about the effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on organizational citizenship behavior in improving employee performance at PT Gelora Persada Mediatama Semarang. Meanwhile, Wijayanti's research (2013) on the support of autonomy and self-efficacy on satisfaction through organizational commitment at PT boma bisma indra. Then the last one is research by Budiarto and Wardani (2005) about messages of distributive justice, procedural justice and company interactional justice on employee commitment to Batteray company.

From the third research above, it is known that previous researchers took case studies or research objects to companies engaged in profit companies, while in this study will try to take research objects engaged in non-profit companies where the main goal of this organization is not solely to seek profit which makes human resources the most valuable asset, because all the activities of this organization are basically from, by and for humans. Based on the explanation above, this study will attempt to fill the gaps available both phenomena and research gaps and explain the effect of Self efficacy and Distributive Justice on Employee Performance mediated by Organizational Commitment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Self efficacy and distributive justice is very influential on employee performance, the higher the employee's ability, the higher the organizational performance. Vice versa, the lower the employee's ability, the lower the organization. Performance is a work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks that have been assigned to him based on skills, experience and sincerity and time (Kasager, 2013).

Hayati (2014: 114) defines organizational commitment as a process of identifying employees with organizational goals. Organizational commitment can also be defined as a psychological state that shows the character of the employee's relationship with the organization and has implications for the decision to continue membership in the organization (Allen & Meyer, 2013). Therefore, it can be said that the higher the commitment possessed by the employee, the better the performance will be. Organizational commitment here reflects the individual's positive attitude towards the organization, knowledge and understanding of organizational commitment can be used as a basis for predicting work behavior (Sehertian and Soetjipto, 2011). Someone who has high efficacy tends to use all the abilities they have to achieve the expected goals. Another factor that affects performance is distributive justice related to the distribution of resources and the criteria that determine the allocation of these resources, concerning the problem of a person's perception of the fairness of the career they receive (Palupi et.al, 2014).

Self efficacy or self-efficacy is a belief in a person's ability to face and solve problems, as well as confidence in being able to organize and complete a job in order to achieve a certain level of performance (May, 2013). Self-efficacy is one of the personal factors that become intermediaries or mediators in the interaction between behavioral factors and environmental factors. Self-efficacy can be a determinant of the success of job performance and implementation (Lodjo, 2013).

Hypothesis

1. *Self efficacy* to organizational commitment

Subagyo (2014) that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. The regression results provide evidence that self-efficacy has a dominant influence on organizational commitment with a regression coefficient of 0.358. That people with high self-efficacy tend not to give up easily when faced with work difficulties. However complex the tasks and work that must be done, people with high self-efficacy will tend to be motivated to be able to complete, there is no motivation to leave their job or organization just because of difficulties or obstacles in carrying out their duties and work. Based on previous research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H1: Self efficacy has a positive effect on organizational commitment.

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2. Distributive justice to organizational commitment

Budiarto and Wardani (2005) in their research found that the company's distributive justice is more dominant in influencing employee commitment to the company than the company's interactional and procedural justice on the subjects studied, namely employees at the company's operational level. With a significance level of 0.901 for the correlation between distributive justice and firm commitment; 0,506 for the correlation between procedural fairness and company commitment; and 0.624 for the correlation between interactional justice with commitment against the company. Based on previous research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H2: Justice distributive effect positive to commitment organizational.

3. Self efficacy on employee performance

Fajriah and Darokah (2016) in their research, self-efficacy has a direct role in performance with a path coefficient of 0.440 and a P value of less than 0.05. The effective contribution of self-efficacy to performance is 19.4%. These results accept hypothesis 1 which states that there is an effect of self-efficacy on performance, which means that the higher the employee's self-efficacy, the better the performance. Based on previous research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H3: Self efficacy has a positive effect on employee performance.

4. Distributive justice on employee performance

Hidayah and Haryani (2013) in their research stated that distributive justice had a significant effect on the performance of BMT Hudatama Semarang employees. This result is evidenced by the output where the tcount is 2.201 with a significance level of 0.034 <0.05, so it can be concluded that the performance of BMT Hudatama Semarang employees is influenced by distributive justice given by the organization. Based on previous research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H4: Distributive justice has a positive effect on employee performance.

5. Organizational commitment to employee performance

Putrana, et.al (2016) in their research shows that the t-count X2 is 0.315 with a significance value of 0.754, the significance value is > 0.05, then Ho is accepted, thus the hypothesis which states that there is a significant influence between Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance is accepted. . Based on previous research, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H5: organizational commitment has a positive effect on employee performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The time used in this research starts from the preparation of the proposal to the preparation of the research report until the data can actually be collected, namely from October 2020 to June 2021. The area carried out in this research is carried out at the Bali Province Youth and Sports Education Office which having its address at Jl. Raya Puputan No.11, Renon Denpasar.

In this study, the population used by the researchers were all employees in the Department of Education, Youth and Sports of the Province of Bali with a total of 284 employees. According to Ferdinand (2014: 48) in multivariate research (including those using multivariate regression analysis), the sample size is determined as many as 25 times the independent variable. This research uses the Slovin formula. Based on the calculations with the Slovin formula above, the minimum number of samples targeted in the study is 74 people.

The sampling technique in this study is to use purposive sampling, namely the technique of determining the sample with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2010). That means the prospective respondent must have certain criteria. Respondents in this study were employees of the Bali Provincial Education Office. Characteristics of respondents include age, gender, and education.

Inferential analysis technique is used to test the empirical model and hypotheses proposed in this study. The analysis technique used is a structural equation model (Structural Equation Modeling - SEM) based on variance or component based SEM, known as Partial Least Square (PLS).

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis test

Direct Effect Test

The basis used in testing the hypothesis is the value contained in the output result for inner weight. The results of hypothesis testing in this study are presented in table 1 below:

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Table 1. Direct Effect Test Results

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	Conclusion
<i>Self Efficacy (X1)</i> Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.386	3.889	H-1 Accepted
Distributive Justice (X2) Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.352	2,938	H-2 Accepted
<i>Self Efficacy (X1)</i> Employee Performance (Y)	0.315	2,396	H-3 Accepted
Distributive Justice (X2) Employee Performance (Y)	0.441	3.017	H-4 Accepted
Organizational Commitment (Z) Employee Performance (Y)	0.241	1971	H-5 Accepted

Data processed, 2021

Mediation testing

The results of the mediation effect test can be presented in a recapitulation table of the results of the mediation effect test which can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Recapitulation of Mediation Variable Test Results

Mediation of Organizational Commitment Variable (Z)	Effect				
	A	B	C	D	Note:
<i>Self Efficacy (X1) -></i> Employee Performance (Y)	0.315 (sig)	0.379 (sig)	0.386 (sig)	0.241 (sig)	<i>Partial Mediation</i>
Distributive Justice (X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.441 (sig)	0.558 (sig)	0.386 (sig)	0.241 (sig)	<i>Partial Mediation</i>

Data processed, 2021

Information that can be obtained from table 2 above is the result of testing the mediating variable which can be conveyed as follows:

1. Organizational commitment is able to mediate the indirect effect of self efficacy (X1) on employee performance (Y). This result is shown from the mediation test conducted, it appears that the effects of C, D, and A have a significant value. The results of this test determine that self-efficacy (X1) can affect employee performance (Y) through organizational commitment (Z), which can be proven empirically. Other information that can be conveyed is the mediating effect of the organizational commitment variable (Y) on the indirect effect of self-efficacy (X1) on employee performance (Y) which is partial mediation. Based on this, it can be concluded that the better organizational commitment with good self-efficacy can also improve the performance of employees at the Bali Provincial Youth and Sports Education Office.
2. Organizational commitment is able to mediate positively and significantly on the indirect effect of distributive justice (X2) on employee performance (Y). It is shown from the mediation test that the effects of C, A and D have a significant value. The results of this test determine that distributive justice (X2) can affect employee performance (Y) through organizational commitment (Z) can be proven empirically. Based on this, it can be concluded that the better the existing organizational commitment with the implementation of good organizational justice, it can also improve the performance of employees at the Bali Provincial Sports Education and Youth Office. Other information that can be conveyed is the mediating effect of organizational commitment variable (Z) on the indirect effect of organizational justice (X2) on employee performance (Y) is partial mediation. This finding is an indication that the organizational commitment variable

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(Z) is not a determinant of the effect of distributive justice (X2) on employee performance (Y).

In order to find out the overall effect for each relationship between the variables studied, it can be recapitulated the direct effect, indirect effect and total effect which are presented in Table 5.15 as follows:

Table 3. Calculation of direct, indirect and total effects

No	Variable relationship	Immediate effect	Indirect effect	Total effect
1	<i>Self Efficacy</i> (X1)-> Organizational commitment (Z)	0.386		0.386
2	Distributive Justice (X2) ->Organizational commitment (Z)	0.352		0.352
3	<i>Self efficacy</i> (X1) ->Employee performance (Y)	0.315	0.093 (0.241* 0.386)	0.408
4	Distributive Justice (X2) - >Employee Performance (Y)	0.441	0.085 (0.241*0.352)	0.526
5	Organizational Commitment (Z) ->Employee performance (Y)	0.241		0.241

Data processed, 2021

The information obtained from Table 5.16 above is that the mediating effect of the organizational commitment variable (Z) on the indirect effect of the organizational justice variable (X2) on employee performance (Y) is greater than the indirect effect of self-efficacy (X2) on employee performance (Y). This finding provides an indication that organizational justice perceived by employees has a more dominant effect in growing organizational commitment so that employees are able to show better performance to achieve organizational goals.

RESEARCH DISCUSSION

Self Efficacy affect Organizational Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing state that self-efficacy has a positive effect on organizational commitment, this means that the better the existing self-efficacy, the higher the commitment of employees to work. Self-efficacy as measured by indicators of mastery experience (X1.1), social modeling (X1.2), social persuasion (X1.3), physical and emotion X1.4) can increase organizational commitment. The results of this study are in line with research from Subagyo (2014, The Effect of Self Efficacy on Organizational Commitment through employee job satisfaction. The results show that Self Efficacy has an effect on Organizational Commitment of Education Office employees, the results of research from all variables used Self efficacy has an effect on organizational commitment.

Distributive Justice Affects Organizational Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing state that distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, this means that the better the implementation of distributive justice in the Bali Provincial Education Office, it will increase the organizational commitment of employees to work. Budiarto and Wardani (2005) in their research found that the company's distributive justice is more dominant in influencing employee commitment to the company than the company's interactional and presedural justice on the subjects studied, namely employees in the company's operational department. Distributive justice as measured by indicators of contribution justice (X2.1), compensation (X2.2), promotion (X2.3), rewards (X2.4) can increase organizational commitment.

Self Efficacy affect employee performance

The results of hypothesis testing state that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better self-efficacy in the Bali Provincial Education Office, it will improve employee performance. Self Efficacy as measured by indicators of mastery experience (X1.1), social modeling (X1.2), social persuasion (X1.3), physical (X1.4) can improve employee performance. The results of research from Fajriah and Darokah (2016) that self-efficacy has a direct role on employee performance. Another finding in this study is that organizational commitment is able to mediate the relationship between self-efficacy and employee performance. The better the existing self-efficacy is balanced with organizational commitment, the better employee performance will be.

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Distributive Justice to Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing state that distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better the application of existing distributive justice will increase the performance of the employee to work. The results of research from Hidayah and Haryani (2013) state that distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Distributive justice as measured by indicators of contribution (X2.1), compensation (X2.2), promotion (X2.3), awards (X2.4) can improve employee performance at the Bali Provincial Education Office. Another finding from this study is organizational commitment is able to mediate the effect of distributive justice on employee performance,

Organizational Commitment to Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing state that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better the organizational commitment at the Bali Provincial Education Office, the better the performance of employees to work. The results of research from Putrana, et.al (2016) stated that there was a significant influence between organizational commitment on employee performance and accepted. Organizational commitment as measured by indicators of effective commitment (Z.1), continuous commitment (Z.2), normative commitment (Z.3) can improve employee performance.

RESEARCH IMPLICATION

From the results of the research and discussion above, it can be stated that the research implications are:

1. *Self efficacy* which prioritizes social persuasion can improve employee performance at the Bali Provincial Education Office, this is reflected in the increase in employee performance achievements in the quality of their work. However, self-efficacy has not been able to be used as a basis for employees to commit to the organization to improve performance.
2. Distributive justice that prioritizes rewards can improve employee performance at the Bali Provincial Education Office, however distributive justice that can improve employee performance will be more decisive if it is used as a basis for employees to commit. In other words, employees will be committed to working at the Bali Provincial Education Office based on the sense of fairness that they receive in their work will provide greater results in significant achievements.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of the research results, it can be concluded that the analysis of the influence of the variable self-efficacy, distributive justice on organizational commitment in improving employee performance is:

1. *Self efficacy* has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, this means that the better the existing self-efficacy, the higher the organizational commitment at the Bali Provincial Sports Education and Youth Office, and vice versa, the worse the existing self-efficacy, the lower the organizational commitment at the Youth Education Office. and Bali Province Sports.
2. Distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, this is the better the application of existing distributive justice will increase organizational commitment at the Bali Provincial Education and Youth and Sports Office, and vice versa the worse the implementation of existing organizational justice, the commitment will decrease. organizational structure at the Bali Province Youth and Sports Education Office.
3. *Self efficacy* positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better the existing self-efficacy, the higher the employee's performance at the Bali Province Education and Youth and Sports Office and vice versa, the worse the existing self-efficacy, the lower the employee's performance.
4. Distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better the implementation of existing distributive justice, the better the performance of employees at the Bali Provincial Education and Youth and Sports Office. Vice versa, the worse the implementation of existing distributive justice, the lower the employee's performance will be.
5. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this means that the better the existing organizational commitment, the better the performance of employees at the Bali Province Youth and Sports Education Office, and vice versa, the worse the existing organizational commitment, the lower the employee's performance. .

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Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, the suggestions that can be submitted in this study are as follows:

1. The results of the study obtained a greater value on distributive justice to organizational commitment. So the implications for employees are expected to increase employee commitment to the organization.
2. The Bali Provincial Education Office needs to implement distributive justice, for example by giving awards to employees who deserve it. Giving awards to employees who excel can encourage employees to maintain and improve their performance.
3. In improving the performance of employees at the Bali Provincial Education Office, they should pay more attention to the quality of work than employees to improve better performance.
4. For the next researcher, it is hoped that it is necessary to study further about the factors that can improve employee performance other than self-efficacy, such as distributive justice, and organizational commitment.

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